

METHODOLOGY FOR IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL QUALITIES OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract: In this article, we describe the methods of professional competence development of primary school teachers and their work.

Key words: competence, professional competence, personal experience, technologies, practical activity, development.

Introduction.

Modern society requires the education system to educate highly qualified, aspiring, competitive, enterprising, spiritually and physically healthy individuals. In the action strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, the task of "educating a highly educated and intellectually developed generation, creating a pool of competent scientific and pedagogical personnel in higher education institutions" was set. Competent pedagogue - who is he? Questions arise, such as how the process of its formation takes place. In this context, it is important to define the meaning of the concepts "competence" and "competence". Not every teacher knows what "competence" means and how it differs from "competence".

The concept of "competence" includes education, skills, abilities and experience of the pedagogue. In other words, it is his ability to perform a certain type of work. Actually, both terms are similar.

The teacher's professional training and component development is an integral part of the educational process. Therefore, improvement of didactic training is considered by L. S. Podimova as one of the decisive conditions for building the educational process on a scientific basis and is seen as a method that increases the productivity of pedagogical work. N. A. Shaydenko analyzes didactic training as a factor in the successful formation of the teacher's teaching function [2.89]. R. P. Skulsky calls didactic training and conducts scientific research on the main directions of professional training and education of future teachers. V. G. Podzolkov writes about didactic training and considers it as the main component of teacher development.

If the professional skills program of the pedagogue is looked at practically, then its integral quality - the teacher's skills - will be in the first place. Despite the fact that there are so many definitions of pedagogical skill, some aspects of the skill are definitely expressed in them.

Mastery is a high and ever-evolving art of education and training. A pedagogue is a master of his work, an in-depth knowledge of his subject, well-acquainted with relevant fields of science and art, a good understanding of general and youth psychology in practice, a comprehensive knowledge of teaching and upbringing methodology, and a highly cultured person. expert. There are two different understandings of teacher skills in pedagogical theory.

The first is related to the understanding of pedagogical work, and the second is that the personality of the pedagogue plays a key role in education.

Competence refers to the totality of knowledge and its availability in people, while competence refers to the level of use of knowledge in the work process. There are several approaches to the definition of competencies: - In the American approach, competencies are considered as patterns of employee behavior. If the employee has the necessary skills and knowledge, he will show good results. - In the European approach, competencies are seen as a description of work tasks and expected work results, that is, the ability to act in accordance with accepted standards. In the State Educational Standard of General Secondary Education, approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 187 of April 6, 2017, the concept of competence is defined as the ability to apply existing knowledge, skills and abilities in daily activities.

A. I. Uman considers the improvement of didactic training as one of the most important tasks of pedagogical education [5.106]. T. A. Spirina describes didactic education as the main training in the general pedagogical training system. However, for researchers, with the exception of Ukrainian colleagues R. P. Skulsky and V. I. Grinev, the problem of the development of the didactic culture of the teacher as a problem in the process of didactic training and does not solve it. So it is considered a normal situation for them to be mastered during their studies.[5.78]

In our country, all conditions and opportunities have been created for bringing up young people who are active, aspiring, talented and have high spiritual and moral qualities, who have acquired modern knowledge and professions - who are the decisive force of our today and tomorrow. Today, the development of science and technology requires a fundamental change in the requirements for education and its results. Based on this, the creation of new generation standards is an important task for pedagogues. State educational standards created until now were based on a systematic-active approach, that is, clarifying the purpose of educational institutions in the way of mastering knowledge, skills and abilities. Therefore, it is required to set new state educational standards based on the competent-active approach aimed at self-development.

Competence is the Latin word "Competentia", the dictionary meaning of which in Uzbek means "a person who knows well", "having experience". Competence is the ability to do a job effectively, the ability to meet the requirements in the performance of work, the ability to meet the requirements in the performance of specific work functions [2.89]. Professional competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level [5.61].

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